

AN ANALYSIS OF THE NEUTRALISATION CURVES OF THE COLLOIDAL ACIDS. PART I

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The neutralisation curves of the colloidal acids have been interpreted as the neutralisation of macromolecular polybasic acid particles, as if present in true solution. A method has been suggested for approaching the polybasic acid (containing a single type of acidic groups) neutralisation curve graphically and quantitatively. The initial slope of such a curve is monobasic, and in fact, the whole curve is monobasic everywhere, only the active acidity and the dissociation constant have different values for different points on the curve. As a titration proceeds, the active acidity gradually increases and the dissociation constant drifts to lower and lower values. Whereas in the neutralisation of a monobasic acid in true solution the $-ve$ logarithm of the dissociation constant (pK value) is a fixed point at half neutralisation, here in the case of the polybasic acid it has been found to lie on a smooth continuous curve, the change being nowhere abrupt. Simultaneous ion-adsorption considerably masks this monobasic behaviour and sometimes produces an apparent impression of the presence of a strong acid and also of a discontinuity in the dissociation constant relationship. In many cases the experimental curve is the resultant of two curves, one due to ion adsorption and the other due to neutralisation as in true solution.

The potentiometric titration curves of colloidal acids are in several respects different from those of acids in true solution (Mukherjee, Mitra and Mukherjee, *Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1937, 1, 227). The nature of the titration curves has been broadly interpreted on the basis of the theory of the electrical double layer *vis a vis* the interaction of the ions in the double layer with those in the bulk of the solution, but no attempt has been made to interpret quantitatively the entire course of the titration curves. The existing picture of the double layer does not seem to lend itself to mathematical treatment because the parameters involved are more or less of uncertain magnitude.

The present communication records, firstly, a somewhat different picture concerning the interaction between ions in solution and those associated with colloidal particles, and secondly, it derives, based on the above formulation, relationships between the pH and added alkali concentration, of some of the possible types of the colloidal acids, and finally brings, in the way of verifying the above relationships, some published information on the potentiometric studies of a silicic acid sol.

The proposed picture in a colloidal system, composed of negatively charged particles, envisages a certain degree of aggregation, probably, as a result of the bonding between the exchangeable cations and the colloidal particles. A somewhat similar picture has been invoked to explain the formation of soil crumbs (Russell, *Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, 233A, 361), but we have reasons to think that a definite amount of aggregation always exists even in apparently well-dispersed sols, viz., clay sols. No account has been taken, in the proposed model, of the crystalline nature of the colloidal particles, primarily because we are concerned with the reactions on the surface of the aggregates and in the surrounding solution, which may be supposed to be independent of the detailed core structure except for the fact that such quantities as ion-adsorbing capacities

$$(a_{H^+})_f = (a_{H^+})_L \times (V_L/V_s)$$

or

$$(p_H)_f = (p_H)_L + \log (V_s/V_L) = (p_H)_L + \text{constant},$$

i.e., the corrected neutralisation curve will be slightly raised parallel to that drawn on the basis of observed p_H . As V_L approaches V_s , the difference between the two becomes negligible.

Depending on the relative proportions of the two categories of H^+ ions, three cases may arise, two of which, (A) and (B), refer almost exclusively to either category being present, and the third, (C), to the presence of both categories of H^+ ions.

A. The Hydrogen-ion Activity due to Colloid is present only in the Micellar solution: This is a hypothetical case. The assumption is that there is no contribution to the H^+ ion activity in the intermicellar solution from the surface of the colloidal particles, *i.e.*, the active groups, marked 'a' in Fig 1, are absent. On the addition of an alkali, say NaOH, Na^+ ions take the place of H^+ ions present in the micellar solution, and hence, at any instant of the titration,

$$(a_{H^+})_a + (a_{Na^+})_a = C_a \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where $(a_{H^+})_a$ and $(a_{Na^+})_a$ denote the H^+ and Na^+ activities at any instant and C_a , the initial activity of the H^+ ions in the micellar solution calculated over the whole suspension. Complete neutralisation would mean $C_a = (a_{Na^+})_a$. The total amount 'b' of the added alkali which may be distributed between the two solutions is at any instant given by

$$b = (a_{Na^+})_a + (a_{Na^+})_f \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

For electroneutrality in the intermicellar solution

$$(a_{Na^+})_f + (a_{H^+})_f = (a_{OH^-})_f \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Also

$$(a_{H^+})_f \times (a_{OH^-})_f = K_w \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where K_w is the ionic product of water.

Applying the Donnan distribution law to each aggregate and summing up for all such aggregates, it can be shown that

$$\frac{(a_{Na^+})_f}{(a_{H^+})_f} = \frac{(a_{Na^+})_a}{(a_{H^+})_a} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

where all the activities are expressed in g. ions/litre of the suspension.

Putting $x = (a_{H^+})_f$ and substituting the values of the activities in equation (5) from equations (1), (2), (3) and (4) and rearranging, one gets

$$b = (K_w/x) + C_a - x - (C_a \cdot x^2/K_w) \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

The curve A corresponding to the above equation is shown in Fig. 2, where $p_H = -\log_{10} x$. Writing equation (6) in terms of p_H , *i.e.*, by replacing x by (10^{-p_H}) and equating $(d^2 p_H / db^2)$ to 0, one gets

$$b - C_a = 3 \cdot C_a \cdot (x^2/K_w)$$

Since (x^2/K_n) is very small at the inflexion point, the corresponding value of 'b' is virtually equal to C_n , the amount of H^+ ions inside the aggregate, which is the total acidity in this case.

B. The Hydrogen-ion Activity due to Colloid is present only in the Intermicellar solution: This case visualises a well-dispersed sol in which the H^+ ions are so disposed with reference to the solid phase that they can freely ionise in the intermicellar solution, i.e., the groups marked 'b' in Fig. 1, are absent. The degree of ionisation will be different at different p_n due to the influence which the size of the colloidal particles, the distance between the ionisable groups and their chemical nature may exert. The polybasicity of the colloidal particles may arise from one or more of these factors. The dissociation constants are therefore likely to have fixed values but may drift in an almost continuous manner as the neutralisation proceeds. For the same type of ionisable groups, the neutralisation curve is expected to be continuous because only when K_{n-1}/K_n is higher than 16, the titration curve with an alkali will show a break (Auerbach and Smolczyk, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 110, 65). This is particularly so when the acidic groups are weakly ionisable. The mathematical treatment becomes complicated in such cases. In a polybasic colloidal acid particle all the ionisable H atoms have equal probability of ionisation, but once one group ionises, the probability is greatest for the remotest hydrogen atom, for the latter will be least influenced by the positive hydrogen ion atmosphere developed surrounding the negative charge. It has been shown (Gane and Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2153) that the ratio K_1/K_2 of dibasic acids of the type $(CH_2)_n(COOH)_2$ decreases from 734 to 7.30 as 'n' increases from 1 to 7. This means that K_2 shows a large proportionate increase as the chain length increases from 2.44 Å, when $n=1$, to 11.79 Å, when $n=7$.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

The distance between ionisable groups on a colloidal acid particle is much more enlarged than what happens on a molecular level, and hence, the ionisation of several acidic groups, separated by quite large distances, on a particular particle, may occur almost independent of one another. Considering all the particles, it is therefore possible to think of a small assembly of ionisable groups constituting a fraction of the total acidity

having dissociation energies not far removed from an average value. In that case the assembly behaves as a monobasic acid of concentration, C_1 , and dissociation constant, k_1 . A number of such assemblies of ionisable groups may thus be envisaged which differ in their concentration and dissociation constant. Thus, the entire neutralisation curve may be constructed by characterising different stretches of the curve with decreasing dissociation constants $k_1, k_2, k_3, \dots, k_n$ and corresponding monobasic acidities $C_1, C_2, C_3, \dots, C_n$ (as shown in curve A of Fig. 3.), where C_n represents the total acidity, C_1 .

Let the first assembly of acid groups, which can be treated as a monobasic acid, have a concentration, C_1 , and a dissociation constant, k_1 . Then with reference to the equilibrium $HR \rightleftharpoons H^+ + R^-$

$$(a_n^-)_1 = \frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

(by eliminating a_{HR} from the expression for k_1 and the relation $C_1 = a_n^- + a_{HR}$). This value of $(a_n^-)_1$ when introduced in the electroneutrality relation,

$$(a_{Na^+})_1 = (a_{OH^-})_1 + (a_n^-)_1 - (a_n^+)_1,$$

one gets

$$b = (K_w/x) + \frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} - x \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) (corresponding to FQR) predicts the course of the neutralisation curve up to a certain point (stretch PQ in curve A, Fig. 3). A second similar equation with C_2 and k_2 (curve NQ'T'S) will hold good for the next stretch (QT) and so on. Equation (8) may be analysed further for the case when $b=0$. By neglecting K_w/x , i.e. a_{OH^-} in acid solution, one gets

$$X^2 + k_1 X = C_1 k_1 \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

where X , the initial H^+ ion activity, replaces x . Considering C_1 proportional to the colloid content, 'A', for the same stock suspension, equation (9) becomes $X^2 + k_1 X = \alpha A k_1$, where ' α ' is the proportionality factor. This expresses the variation of H^+ concentration with colloid content. Pallmann (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1930, 30, 354), who studied this variation with a number of colloids, obtained linear relationships only at low "relative concentrations". At high "relative concentrations", deviation from linearity was observed by him in the case of a palmitic acid sol and an electro-dialysed clay suspension. The above parabolic equation, it will be seen from the data in columns 2, 3, 4 and 5 of Table I(A and B), gives a better fit than Pallmann's linear relationship. The values of C_1 corresponding to relative concentration 100, and k_1 are respectively $2.54 \times 10^{-5} N$ and 7×10^{-5} for palmitic acid sol and $4.16 \times 10^{-5} N$ and 20×10^{-5} for the clay suspension (Gupta, *Science & Culture*, 1956, 21, 547). k_1 for the palmitic acid sol is more or less of the same order as one gets for the first dissociation constant of many polycarboxylic acids in true solution. A similar parabolic curve has been observed in the case of a bentonite suspension by Mukherjee and Mitra (*J. Coll. Sci.*, 1946, 1, 141), at a low relative concentration.

TABLE I

A. Palmitic acid sol.				B. Electrolysed clay suspension.			
		H ⁺ ion concentration.				H ⁺ ion concentration.	
Relative conc.	Obs.	Pallmann.	Calc. from eq. (9).	Relative conc.	Obs.	Pallmann.	Calc. from eq. (9).
0	2.07 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.34 × 10 ⁻⁶		0.0	2.3 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.4 × 10 ⁻⁶	...
10	3.95	3.12	2.5 × 10 ⁻⁶	9.7	4.9	4.6	3.9 × 10 ⁻⁶
25	4.90	5.78	5.9	18.2	6.3	7.4	7.0
40	7.95	8.44	9.0	28.2	9.6	10.7	11.1
50	9.56	10.22	11.0	33.3	11.8	12.5	13.0
75	13.80	14.66	15.6	37.8	13.8	13.9	14.6
100	20.40	19.04	20.1	50.0	19.1	18.0	18.9
200	34.60	35.40	34.2	66.6	25.1	25.6	24.7
300	48.20	54.40	46.1	100	33.9	34.8	35.2
400	56.40	72.10	56.4	200	68.9	68.2	63.2
500	61.40	89.80	65.2	400	108.2	133.9	108.0
600	64.60	107.50	74.1	800	144.6	268.6	176.5
700	68.80	123.90	82.0	Paste	152.6	914.0	...

C. The Hydrogen-ion Activity due to Colloid is present both in the Micellar and in the Intermicellar solution: (a). If the ionisable group has a strong acid function, e.g., $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ and $-\text{CH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H}$, the intermicellar groups, i.e., the groups marked 'a' in Fig. 1, will be all ionised, i.e., $C_i = (a_n^-)_i$. The equation (10) similar to equation (6) may be obtained by evaluating the activities in equation (5). This will simply replace K_w/x term in equation (6) by $(K_w/x) + (a_n^-)_i$, i.e., $(K_w/x) + C_i$.

$$b = C_a + C_i + \frac{K_w}{x} - \frac{C_a \cdot x}{\frac{K_w}{x} + C_i} - x \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

The theoretical curve (curve C, Fig. 2) resembles features of a strong acid simulating the titration curves of Dowex 50 and Dowex 30 (Tompkins, *J. Chem. Ed.*, 1949, 26, 35) containing strong acid groups and yet differs from a strong acid (curve B, Fig. 2).

At $b=0$, neglecting K_w/x , the initial H^+ ion activity $X = C_i$ from equation (10). C_i is, however, a part of the acid representing intermicellar groups only, and therefore the total acidity cannot be calculated from the initial p_H unlike what one gets in the case of a strong acid. At $p_H = 7.0$, $x = K_w/x = 10^{-7}$ one gets from equation (10)

$$b = C_a + C_i - \frac{C_a \cdot 10^{-7}}{10^{-7} + C_i}$$

The last term being extremely small, $b = C_a + C_i$, i.e., the amount of alkali required to neutralise the acid at $p_H 7.0$ is equivalent to both categories of H^+ ions although the initial p_H registered is situated higher than that corresponding to the total acidity.

(b). The ionisable groups have a weak acid function, i.e., the groups marked 'a' are partially ionised as in Fig. 1, and are neutralised as a polybasic acid, the initial stretch simulating the neutralisation of a monobasic acid, C_i , constituting a fraction of the total acidity, C_i .

The following equation can be derived in which $C_1 k_1 / (k_1 + x)$ has replaced $(a_n^-)_f = C_f$ in equation (10).

$$b = C_a + \frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} + \frac{K_w}{x} - \frac{C_a \cdot x}{\frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} + \frac{K_w}{x}} - x \quad \dots (11)$$

The theoretical curve PQ'R' for this equation is shown in curve B, Fig. 3., which deviates from the polybasic curve PQ'M' at the point Q' for reasons stated earlier. This type of curve is given by silicic acid sol, colloidal clay acid and some colloidal acid resins. Some of the experimental curves and data, obtained by Mukherjee *et al.* (*Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1936, 6, 517), are shown respectively in Figs. 4-6, and in Table II. They may be analysed as follows. Depending on the method of preparation, silicic acid sol contains a trace of free HCl, estimated quantitatively by ultrafiltration. Accordingly, $(a_n^-)_f$ has to be corrected for by adding to it the $(a_{Cl^-})_f = r$, say. Moreover, at low p_n , K_w/x may be neglected and equation (11) takes the form (11a).

$$b = C_a + \frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} + r - \frac{C_a \cdot x}{\frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + x} + r} - x \quad \dots (11a)$$

by putting $b = 0$, $x = X$, the initial H^+ ion activity, one gets

$$X = \frac{C_1 k_1}{k_1 + X} + r \quad \dots (11b)$$

The initial p_n of the silicic acid sol, (sol H) and the diluted sols, has been calculated from this relationship and shown in the last column of Table II. Also $C_a + r = 14.4 \times 10^{-5} N$ and $r = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} N$ so that $C_a = 9.4 \times 10^{-5} N$. When the p_n rises by about two units, the last two terms in equation (11a) are of the order of 10^{-7} and can be neglected in comparison to the rest of the terms which are of the order of 10^{-5} . On rearrangement, since $x = X \cdot 10^{-\Delta p_n}$, one gets $C_1 k_1 = (b - C_a - r) (k_1 + X \cdot 10^{-\Delta p_n}) \dots (12)$ where Δp_n is the rise in p_n above the initial value.

TABLE II
Conc. of sol in g. mol. of SiO_2 /litre = 0.233.

System.	Acid at inflexion.	p_n .	Total Cl ⁻ .	p_n calc. from eq. (11b).
Sol H	$14.4 \times 10^{-5} N$	4.10 (Quinhydrone) 4.02 (Pt-H ₂)	$5.0 \times 10^{-3} N$	4.24
Sol H/2	7.2	4.30 (Quinhydrone) 4.16 (Pt-H ₂)		4.50
Sol H/5	3.1	4.60 (Quinhydrone) 4.09 (Pt-H ₂)		4.82
Sol H/10	1.6	4.67 (Quinhydrone) 4.14 (Pt-H ₂)		5.03
Sol H/20	0.8	4.91 (Quinhydrone) 5.09 (Pt-H ₂)		5.14
Ultrafiltrate of Sol H			5.0	

k_1 may be solved in terms of X by considering two successive values of $C_1 k_1$, treating it as a constant over the range. These calculations are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Δp_n .	Conc. of alkali added ($b \times 10^3$).	$C_1 k_1 \times 10^6$.	k_1 .
1.5	32.5	18.1 ($k_1 + 0.03162 X$)	0.0085 X
1.6	36.0	21.6 ($k_1 + 0.02572 X$)	0.0084 X
1.7	40.0	25.6 ($k_1 + 0.01995 X$)	0.0075 X
1.8	44.5	30.1 ($k_1 + 0.01585 X$)	

Taking $k_1 = 0.0084 X$, C_1 becomes equal to 86.4×10^{-5} using equation (12). From equation (11b), $X = 5.725 \times 10^{-3}$ corresponding to p_n 4.24. Hence, $k_1 = 4.809 \times 10^{-7}$. Inserting these values in equation (11a), the theoretical titration curve for silicic acid sol H is obtained and compared with the experimental one in Fig. 4. The curve for sol H/2, also shown in Fig. 4, has been constructed keeping k_1 constant with the values of C_1 , τ and C_2 exactly halved. The curve for the third sol, sol H/5, (Fig. 5), necessitates calculations of C_2 and k_2 for stretches beyond C_1 from the slope of the curve and are found to be 262×10^{-5} and 8.03×10^{-8} respectively. For the construction of curves for sol H/10 and sol H/20, shown in Fig. 6, the initial stretches have been computed by using proper fractions of C_1 and C_2 together with the dissociation constants, k_1 and k_2 . For the construction of stretches beyond C_2 , a third dissociation constant k_3 (2.6×10^{-8}) and acidity C_3 (546×10^{-5}) have been used.

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

It will be seen from Fig. 4, that the theoretical and experimental curves run nearly parallel. This small difference often occurs even between two experimental curves for the same sol, as shown by the two experimental curves for sol H. The dotted lines

with the experimental curves for sol H/2, sol H/5 and sol H/10 show what could have been a better fit. The deviation may be due to contamination of KCl from the ground-in glass junction of the salt bridge, as a result of which H^+ ions are likely to be exchanged and released from $(H^+)_n$ by K^+ ions, indicating a lower p_x .

FIG. 6

It is an experimental fact that the potentiometric titration curves of silicic acid sols and clay acids show different features depending upon the nature of the cation of the base used to titrate them. Thus, while $NaOH$ and KOH show a weak acid feature, $Ca(OH)_2$ and $Ba(OH)_2$ suggest strong acid features. On the basis of the double layer theory, the discrepancy has been explained by the fact that the bivalent cations are more strongly adsorbed and form ion-pairs; consequently they show greater buffering characteristic of strong acids. According to the picture presented here, we would say, that the bivalent cations increase aggregation as they are definitely known to do so, and thereby increase the value of C_n , and according to case A, this will impart a strong acid character to the system. This idea may easily be extended to understand the higher observed acidity of the colloidal acids when titrated with bases in presence of neutral salts than when titrated alone. A quantitative treatment of these cases requires a more definite knowledge of the aggregates than what is available at present. In our next communication we will deal with some clay acid titrations in the light of the above formulations.

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